

Extended Data File 6: Included articles and policy documents with characteristics and quality assessment ratings (N=45)

Article	Year	Country	Intervention	Policy Doc	Provided data for Theories	Age of pts	Relevance 0-3	Rigor 0-3	Richness 0-4	Richness at extraction
Anderson, K., et al. (2020). "GP-Led Deprescribing in Community-Living Older Australians: An Exploratory Controlled Trial." <u>Journal of the American Geriatrics Society</u> 68 (2): 403-410.	2020	Australia	Y		T1, T3, T4, T5, T6	≥65	3	3	3	3
Cantrill, J. A., et al. (2011). "Qualitative insights into general practitioners' views on the appropriateness of their long-term prescribing." <u>International Journal of Pharmacy Practice</u> 8 (1): 20-26.	2011	UK	No		T1, T2, T3, T5, T6.	not given	2	2	3	3
Chen, Z. and A. Buonanno (2017). "Geriatric Polypharmacy: Two Physicians' Personal Perspectives." 33 (2): 283-288.	2017	USA	No		T1, T2, T5, T6	≥65	2	1	3	2
Clyne, B., et al. (2013). "Addressing potentially inappropriate prescribing in older patients: development and pilot study of an intervention in primary care (the OPTI-SCRIPT study)." 13 (1): 307.	2013	Ireland	Yes		T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	≥70	3	3	3	3
Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "'Potentially inappropriate or specifically appropriate?' Qualitative evaluation of general practitioners views on prescribing, polypharmacy and potentially inappropriate prescribing in older people." <u>BMC family practice</u> 17 (1): 109-109.	2016 ^a	Ireland	No		T1, T2, T3, T5, T6	≥70	3	3	3	3

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Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "A process evaluation of a cluster randomised trial to reduce potentially inappropriate prescribing in older people in primary care (OPTI-SCRIPT study)." <u>Trials</u> 17 (1): 386-386.	2016 b	Ireland	Yes		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	≥70	3	3	3	3
Clyne, B., et al. (2017). "Beliefs about prescribed medication among older patients with polypharmacy: a mixed methods study in primary care." <u>The British journal of general practice : the journal of the Royal College of General Practitioners</u> 67 (660): e507-e518.	2017	Ireland	Yes		T1, T3, T5, T6	≥70	2	3	3	3
Fried, T. R., et al. "Primary care clinicians' experiences with treatment decision making for older persons with multiple conditions." 171 (1): 75-80.	2011	USA	No		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	older persons	3	3	3	3
Geurts, M. M. E., et al. (2016). "Implications of a clinical medication review and a pharmaceutical care plan of polypharmacy patients with a cardiovascular disorder." 38 (4): 808-815.	2016	Netherlands	Yes		T1, T4, T5, T6	≥60	2	3	3	3
Halli-Tierney, A. D., et al. "Polypharmacy: Evaluating Risks and Deprescribing." 100 (1): 32-38.	2019	USA	No		T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	≥18	2	3	3	3
Health Information and Quality Authority, Medicines Management Guidance	2015	Ireland	No	X	T2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Health Service Executive, National Framework for the Integrated Prevention and Management of Chronic Disease in Ireland 2020-2025.	2020	Ireland	No	X	T1, T2, T4, T5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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Heser, K., et al. (2018). "Perspective of elderly patients on chronic use of potentially inappropriate medication - Results of the qualitative CIM-TRIAD study." PLOS ONE 13(9): e0202068-e0202068.	2018	Germany	No		T2, T5	≥75	2	3	3	3
Hoisnard, L., et al. "Do older adults know the purpose of their medications? A survey among community-dwelling people." 75(2): 255-263.	2018	Switzerland	No		T5	≥65 (68+)	2	2	3	2
Hughes, L. D., et al. "Guidelines for people not for diseases: the challenges of applying UK clinical guidelines to people with multimorbidity." 42(1): 62-69.	2013	UK	No		T2	Multi morbid	2	3	3	3
Irish College of General Practitioners, Quick Reference Guide. Medication Review – A Guide for GPs.	2020	Ireland	No	X	T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Jäger, C., et al. (2015). "Design and delivery of a tailored intervention to implement recommendations for multimorbid patients receiving polypharmacy into primary care practices." Biomed Res Int 2015: 938069.	2015	Germany	yes		T1, T2, T4, T5	≥50	3	3	4	4
Jäger, C., et al. (2017). "A tailored programme to implement recommendations for multimorbid patients with polypharmacy in primary care practices—process evaluation of a cluster randomized trial." Implementation Science 12(1): 31.	2017 b	Germany	yes		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	≥50	3	3	4	4

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Jäger, C., et al. (2017). "Impact of a tailored program on the implementation of evidence-based recommendations for multimorbid patients with polypharmacy in primary care practices—results of a cluster-randomized controlled trial." <i>Implementation science: IS</i> 12 (1): 8-8.	2017 a	Germany	Yes		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	≥50	3	3	4	4
Koberlein, J., et al. (2013). "General practitioners' views on polypharmacy and its consequences for patient health care." 14 : 119.	2013	Germany	No		T1, T4	≥65	2	3	3	2
Mallet, L., et al. (2007). "The challenge of managing drug interactions in elderly people." 370 : 185-191.	2007	Canada/Belgium	No		T2, T4, T5, T6	Elderly	2	3	3	2
Medical Council and Pharmaceutical Society of Ireland, Safe Prescribing and Dispensing of Controlled Drugs.	2017	Ireland	No	X	T2, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Medicines optimisation: adverse outcomes from potentially inappropriate prescribing in older people living in the community. Medicines Evidence Commentary.	2016	UK	No	X	T2, T5	≥65	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Medicines adherence: involving patients in decisions about prescribed medicines and supporting adherence.	2009	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T3, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Medicines optimisation: the safe and effective use of medicines to enable the best possible outcomes.	2015	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Multimorbidity and polypharmacy Key therapeutic topic.	2017	UK	No	X	T2, T3, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Multimorbidity: clinical assessment and management.	2016	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Shared decision making. Key therapeutic topic.	2019	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Parker, M., et al. (2015). "GPs, medications and older people: A qualitative study of general practitioners' approaches to potentially inappropriate medications in older people." 34 (2): 134-139.	2015	Australia	No		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	75+	2	3	3	3
Patsuree, A., et al. (2016). "Experiences relating to adverse drug reactions in the community: a cross-sectional survey among patients and the general public in Thailand." <u>Expert opinion on drug safety</u> 15 (3): 287-295.	2016	Thailand	No		T5, T6	≥18	2	2	3	2
Peterson, G. M., et al. (2018). "Practice pharmacists and the opportunity to support general practitioners in deprescribing in the older person." <u>Journal of Pharmacy Practice & Research</u> 48 (2): 183-185.	2018	Australia	No		T2, T5, T6	≥75	2	3	4	3
Pohontsch, N. J., et al. (2017). "General practitioners' views on (long-term) prescription and use of problematic and potentially inappropriate medication for oldest-old patients-A qualitative interview study with GPs (CIM-TRIAD study)." 18 (1): 22.	2017	Germany	No		T2, T5	≥85	3	3	4	4

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Reed, R. L., et al. (2015). "Why do older people with multi-morbidity experience unplanned hospital admissions from the community: a root cause analysis." <u>BMC Health Services Research</u> 15 .	2015	Australia	No		T1	≥70	1	3	4	2
Ridge, A., et al. (2019). "Assessing risk of adverse drug reactions in the elderly: a feasibility study." 41 (6): 1483-1490.	2019	Australia	Yes		T1, T4, T6	≥65	3	3	4	3
Rogers, S., et al. (2014). "Medicines management support to older people: understanding the context of systems failure." 4 (7): e005302.	2014	UK	No		T1, T2, T3, T4, T6	≥65	3	3	4	4
Rozsnyai, Z., et al. (2020). "What do older adults with multimorbidity and polypharmacy think about deprescribing? The LESS study - a primary care-based survey." <u>BMC geriatrics</u> 20 (1): 1-11.	2020	Switzerland	No		T1, T2, T5, T6	≥70	2	2	3	3
Schuling, J., et al. (2012). "Deprescribing medication in very elderly patients with multimorbidity: the view of Dutch GPs. A qualitative study." <u>BMC family practice</u> 13 (1): 56-62.	2012	Netherlands	No		T2, T5, T6	Elderly	2	2	3	3
Scottish Government Polypharmacy Model of Care Group, Polypharmacy Guidance, Realistic Prescribing.	2018	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sinnott, C., et al. (2015). "Improving medication management in multimorbidity: development of the Multimorbidity COllaborative Medication Review And DEcision Making (MY COMRADE) intervention using the Behaviour Change Wheel." <u>Implementation Science</u> 10 (1): 132.	2015	Ireland	Yes		T1, T2, T5, T6	Multi morbid	3	3	3	3

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Sinnott, C., et al. (2015). "What to give the patient who has everything? A qualitative study of prescribing for multimorbidity in primary care." Br J Gen Pract 65(632): e184-191.	2015	Ireland	No		T1, T2, T3, T5, T6	Multi morbid	3	3	3	3
Sinnott, C., et al. (2017). "Improving medication management for patients with multimorbidity in primary care: a qualitative feasibility study of the MY COMRADE implementation intervention." <u>Pilot and Feasibility Studies</u> 3(1): 14.	2017	Ireland	Yes		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	Multi morbid	3	3	4	4
Voigt, K., et al. (2016). "Why do family doctors prescribe potentially inappropriate medication to elderly patients?" BMC family practice 17(1): 93.	2016	Germany	No		T1, T2, T4, T5, T6	≥65	2	2	4	4
Wallace, E., et al. (2015). "Managing patients with multimorbidity in primary care." 350: h176.	2015	Ireland	No		T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	Elderly	3	3	3	3
World Health Organisation, Medication Without Harm - Global Patient Safety Challenge on Medication Safety.	2017	WHO	No	X	T1, T2, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Yorkshire and Humber AHSN Improvement Academy and Connected Yorkshire, Effectiveness Matters; Reducing harm from polypharmacy in older people	2017	UK	No	X	T1, T2, T5, T6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A